

1 **Boron isotope evidence for oceanic carbon dioxide leakage during the**
2 **last deglaciation**

3

4 **M. A. Martínez-Botí^{1,*}, G. Marino^{2,3,*}, G. L. Foster¹, P. Ziveri^{2,4}, M. J. Henehan^{1,5},**
5 **J. W. B. Rae^{6,7}, P. G. Mortyn^{2,8}, D. Vance⁹**

6

7 ¹Ocean and Earth Science, National Oceanography Centre Southampton, University
8 of Southampton Waterfront Campus, Southampton SO14 3ZH, UK.

9 ²Institute of Environmental Science and Technology, Universitat Autònoma de
10 Barcelona, Cerdanyola del Vallès 08193, Spain.

11 ³Research School of Earth Sciences, The Australian National University, Canberra
12 2601, Australia.

13 ⁴Earth & Climate Cluster, Department of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Earth and Life
14 Sciences, VU Universiteit Amsterdam, 1081HV Amsterdam, The Netherlands.

15 ⁵ Department of Geology and Geophysics, Yale University, New Haven, Connecticut
16 06511, USA.

17 ⁶Division of Geological and Planetary Sciences, California Institute of Technology,
18 Pasadena 91125, USA.

19 ⁷Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of St Andrews, St
20 Andrews KY16 9AL, UK.

21 ⁸Department of Geography, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Cerdanyola del
22 Vallès 08193, Spain.

23 ⁹Institute of Geochemistry and Petrology, Department of Earth Sciences, ETH Zürich,
24 NW D81.4, Zürich 8092, Switzerland.

25

26 * These authors contributed equally to this work.

27 Atmospheric CO₂ fluctuations over glacial-interglacial cycles remain a major
28 challenge to our understanding of the carbon cycle and the climate system.
29 Leading hypotheses invoke changes in deep ocean carbon storage^{1,2}, likely
30 modulated by processes in the Southern Ocean where much of the deep ocean is
31 ventilated³. A central aspect of these Southern Ocean-centric models is that,
32 during deglaciations, an isolated glacial deep ocean carbon reservoir is re-
33 connected with the atmosphere, driving the atmospheric CO₂ rise observed in ice
34 core records⁴⁻⁶. However, direct documentation of changes in surface oceanic
35 carbon content has so far been impossible, as has the associated transfer of
36 carbon to the atmosphere during deglaciations, because of the lack of proxies
37 that unambiguously reflect the evolution of the oceanic carbonate system. ¹⁴C
38 tracks changes in ocean ventilation⁶, but not in its carbon content, whereas
39 proxies that record increased deglacial upwelling^{4,7} do not constrain the
40 proportion of upwelled carbon that is degassed versus that taken up by the
41 biological pump. Here we apply the boron isotope-pH proxy in planktic
42 foraminifera to two sediment cores from the Subantarctic Atlantic and the
43 Eastern Equatorial Pacific as a more direct tracer of oceanic CO₂ outgassing. We
44 show that surface waters at both locations, which partly derive from deep water
45 upwelled in the Southern Ocean (*refs to be added*), became a significant source of
46 carbon to the atmosphere during the last deglaciation, when atmospheric CO₂
47 was increasing. This oceanic CO₂ outgassing supports the view that the
48 ventilation of a deep ocean carbon reservoir played a key role in the deglacial
49 CO₂ rise, although our results also raise the possibility that processes operating
50 in regions in addition to the Southern Ocean may have been important for the
51 glacial-interglacial ocean-atmosphere exchange of carbon.

52

53 The modern Southern Ocean (SO) is a region of vigorous upwelling of carbon- and
54 nutrient-rich waters³. Much of the upwelled CO₂ is outgassed to the atmosphere, due
55 to incomplete nutrient utilisation in the SO surface³. These waters are then re-
56 subducted as intermediate waters and feed the thermocline of the low-latitude oceans,
57 such as the Eastern Equatorial Pacific (EEP)⁸, which is, currently, one of the main
58 oceanic sources of CO₂ to the atmosphere⁹ (Figure 1). Many of the mechanisms
59 proposed to reduce atmospheric CO₂ during glacial periods focus on a reduction of
60 SO CO₂ leakage, via increased ocean stratification¹⁰ and/or more efficient biological
61 pump (likely boosted by iron fertilisation)¹¹. During deglaciation, this situation was
62 reversed, and previously isolated deep-ocean carbon is thought to be upwelled and re-
63 exposed to the atmosphere⁴.

64

65 Deglacial upwelling of aged, nutrient-rich waters in the SO, and their subsequent
66 advection to the EEP, was suggested on the basis of several proxies^{4,6,7}, e.g., biogenic
67 opal fluxes, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$. Although these reconstructions provide valuable insights
68 into ocean nutrient dynamics, ventilation history, and circulation, none of them
69 directly tracks the ocean-atmosphere CO₂ exchange. For instance, if biological
70 productivity efficiently utilised the upwelled nutrients and carbon, as possibly
71 indicated by the deglacial increase in SO and EEP opal fluxes^{4,12}, then the CO₂
72 leakage to the atmosphere may have been dampened or even negated completely.
73 Similarly, the appearance of low $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ signatures in the upper ocean at a wide number
74 of locations globally during the deglaciation^{7,13,14}, usually taken as evidence for the
75 re-ventilation of nutrient-enriched (low- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) waters, could be modulated by changing
76 air-sea CO₂ fractionation¹³. Finally, perhaps the most compelling evidence to date for

77 the importance of the re-communication of a deep ocean carbon reservoir with the
78 atmosphere via the SO comes from the decrease in $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ in deep waters around
79 Antarctica due to the deglacial break-down of stratification in that region⁶. However,
80 whilst this correlates well with the atmospheric $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ record and the first rise in
81 atmospheric partial pressure of CO_2 ($p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$) during Heinrich Stadial 1 (HS1), there
82 is little response during the second rise of $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ centred on the Younger Dryas
83 (YD).

84

85 There is therefore an urgent requirement for direct evidence for deglacial CO_2
86 variations in the surface waters of key areas of the global ocean, such as the SO and
87 EEP, thereby testing the hypothesis that oceanic CO_2 outgassing was central to the
88 glacial-interglacial $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ rise^{4,7}. We addressed this issue by analysing the boron
89 isotopic composition ($\delta^{11}\text{B}$) of planktic foraminifera, a proxy^{15,16} for oceanic pH that
90 provides a direct link to seawater CO_2 content. [Figure 2](#) compares records of
91 atmospheric CO_2 concentration⁵ with new planktic foraminiferal $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ and Mg/Ca-
92 derived temperature for the Subantarctic Atlantic (site PS2498-1; 44.15°S, 14.23°W,
93 3,783 m water depth) and the EEP (site ODP1238; 1.87°S, 82.78°W, 2,203 m water
94 depth) ([Figure 1](#)). Surface waters at PS2498-1 are currently influenced by water
95 upwelled in the Antarctic Zone and advected northward via Ekman pumping¹⁷, while
96 ODP1238 is mostly influenced by the Equatorial Undercurrent¹⁸, a subsurface current
97 originating in the Western Equatorial Pacific and fed by water masses of Southern
98 Ocean (~70%) and North Pacific (~30%) origin¹⁹. Previous literature has suggested an
99 effective connection between the Subantarctic and the EEP via intermediate waters¹⁸,
100 through a process often referred to as “oceanic tunnelling”^{14,20} (see [Methods](#)).

101

102 The $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ record for the surface-dwelling foraminifer *Globigerina bulloides* in the
103 Subantarctic core PS2498-1 displays an early deglacial to Holocene change of $\sim 1.3\text{‰}$
104 (~ 0.13 pH units; [Figure 2a,b](#)). Unfortunately, the very low abundance of *G. bulloides*
105 prior to ~ 16 ka precluded $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ analyses for the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), which
106 limited our evaluation of the full glacial-interglacial $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ (and pH) shift at this site.
107 The PS2498-1 $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ profile does not exhibit a gradual change through the deglaciation
108 into the Holocene, but features two distinct decreases (lower pH). At the EEP
109 ODP1238, there is a brief negative excursion in the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ of the surface-dweller
110 *Globigerinoides sacculifer* at 19 ka, and the ensuing deglacial decrease is larger
111 ($\sim 2\text{‰} \approx 0.2$ pH units) and more gradual than that recorded by *G. bulloides* at PS2498.
112 ([Figure 2f,g](#); [Extended Data Figure 1](#)).

113

114 To highlight the main patterns of variability in the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -derived time series and to
115 probabilistically account for all the uncertainties associated with our reconstructions,
116 we used a Monte Carlo approach that employs a non-parametric regression (LOESS
117 function; [Figure 2b,c,g,h](#); see [Methods](#)). A comparison of the PS2498-1 and
118 ODP1238 pH records against the pH expected if surface waters remained in
119 equilibrium with the atmosphere ([green lines in Figure 2b,g](#)), reveals “excess” surface
120 ocean acidification in both these areas during deglaciation and early Holocene. To
121 gain further insight into deglacial ocean-atmosphere CO_2 exchange, we use the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -
122 pH data, along with estimates of temperature, salinity, and alkalinity, to calculate the
123 partial pressure of CO_2 in seawater²¹ ($p\text{CO}_2^{\text{sw}}$ – see [Methods](#)). Note that the
124 temperature, salinity, and alkalinity exert only a minor control on $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{sw}}$ (at most
125 ± 13 μatm , ± 15 μatm , and ± 12 μatm , respectively), which is driven mainly by the
126 $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -derived pH, given the strong correlation of pH and $[\text{CO}_2]$ within the ocean

127 carbonate system²¹. The $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{sw}}$ profiles are compared to $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ from ice core
128 records to yield $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ ($\Delta p\text{CO}_2 = p\text{CO}_2^{\text{sw}} - p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$) and, notably, our late Holocene
129 $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ estimates agree well with modern water column data from nearby locations⁹,
130 supporting the accuracy of our $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -pH calibrations (Figure 2c-h).

131

132 Our EEP $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ record reveals that this region became a significant CO_2 source to the
133 atmosphere during deglaciation and early Holocene, reaching a peak of $+90 \pm 16 \mu\text{atm}$
134 (2σ) at ~ 13 ka that exceeds by $\sim 45 \mu\text{atm}$ average modern values at this location⁹
135 (Figure 2h). Comparison with earlier studies in the Western and Central Pacific²²⁻²⁴
136 that reported deglacial $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ values of $+100$ to $\geq +185 \mu\text{atm}$ shows the widespread
137 nature of the CO_2 outgassing in the equatorial Pacific (see Extended Data Figure 2).
138 The $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ data from the Subantarctic Atlantic Ocean also indicate that this region
139 acted as a source of CO_2 to the atmosphere from ~ 16 to ~ 7.5 ka, but in the form of
140 two prominent multi-millennial events, with a maximum of $+50 \pm 18 \mu\text{atm}$ (i.e., ~ 65
141 μatm higher than present-day average values⁹) at ~ 15 ka (Figure 2c).

142

143 The occurrence of upper ocean acidification in the EEP and Subantarctic Atlantic
144 during the deglaciation coincided, within uncertainties, with excursions toward higher
145 opal fluxes at nearby sites^{4,25} (Figure 3a,b,f,g). This observation provides compelling
146 evidence for the hypothesized link between resumption of Antarctic upwelling⁴ and
147 attendant Ekman transport^{8,17} of deep waters enriched in nutrients and $[\text{CO}_2]$, and
148 oceanic $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ rise in the wider SO. It further suggests that advection to the EEP, via
149 oceanic tunnelling, of these CO_2 -rich waters may (at least partly) explain the deglacial
150 $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ maximum documented in ODP1238. This interpretation is corroborated by the
151 broad synchronicity of the acidification phases with excursions toward depleted

152 surface ocean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ at our core locations (Figure 3c,h), with the deglacial rise in the
153 concentration of atmospheric CO_2 (Figure 3e,l), and with the negative shift⁵ of its
154 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.

155

156 However, the differences in the patterns of pH, $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and opal at the two
157 locations (Figure 2, 3, and Extended Data Figure 2), suggest that the EEP record does
158 not merely represent a downstream expression of the deglacial CO_2 outgassing in the
159 SO, and that additional processes and/or CO_2 sources need to be considered to fully
160 explain its structure. SO-sourced intermediate waters incorporate remineralized
161 carbon during transit to the EEP, which may modify their geochemical
162 characteristics²⁶. Additionally, as source waters of the EUC also include North
163 Pacific-origin waters (~30%)¹⁹, these may provide a potential supplementary source²⁷
164 of CO_2 . During the early Holocene, both our $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ records also indicate continued
165 oceanic CO_2 outgassing, yet $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ shows little change. This suggests that ocean
166 outgassing at this time was balanced by CO_2 uptake, possibly due to forest re-growth
167 and peat buildup as the continental ice sheets retreated from the Northern
168 continents^{2,28}, in line with the near contemporaneous rise⁵ in atmospheric $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Figure
169 3e,k).

170

171 Although millennial changes in the mean position of SO frontal systems²⁹, and in the
172 upwelling strength in the EEP due to shifts of the Intertropical Convergence Zone³⁰,
173 have the potential to change $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ at our sites, such changes seem unlikely to exert a
174 dominant influence on our records. If the high $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ spikes we document were
175 driven by a northward shift of the regional oceanic fronts (PS2498-1) or increased
176 upwelling (ODP1238), they should be accompanied by surface cooling, whereas both

177 sites feature a warming trend during these intervals (Figure 2 and Methods). It is also
178 unlikely that the signals are driven by migration in foraminifera habitat depth. In the
179 Subantarctic, pH vertical gradients are small while, in the EEP, migration to deeper
180 more-acidic waters is inconsistent with the warming signal in Mg/Ca (Figure 2) and
181 with the structural similarity of *G. sacculifer* $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records with those for the
182 strict surface-dweller *Globigerinoides ruber* (see Methods and Extended Data Figure
183 2).

184

185 Local changes in the efficiency of the biological pump, stimulated by Fe-fertilisation,
186 also have the potential³ to influence surface water $p\text{CO}_2$. The evidence that the EEP
187 was a weaker CO_2 source (or even a sink) during the LGM may be ascribed to a dust-
188 bound relaxation of Fe-limitation and attendant strengthening of the biological
189 pump^{12,31}. It is also possible that the gradual decrease in the Fe supply to the EEP and
190 Subantarctic regions during the deglaciation^{11,31} could explain part of the high
191 deglacial $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ at these sites. However, the marked differences between the
192 structure of the dust flux records and our $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ reconstructions argue against this
193 hypothesis (Extended Data Figure 3).

194

195 It therefore seems most plausible that the $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ pulses that we report here using
196 planktic foraminifera $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ reflect oceanic CO_2 outgassing during the last deglaciation.
197 A common origin for the $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ anomalies likely involved the renewed upwelling of
198 aged⁶ deep water enriched in nutrients⁴ and carbon in the Southern Ocean, which
199 subsequently “leaked” to the atmosphere contributing to the deglacial $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ rise
200 and the atmospheric $\Delta^{14}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ decreases^{5,32}. Our analysis also implicates that

201 other carbon sources, possibly located in the wider Pacific Ocean, may need to be
202 invoked to fully explain glacial-interglacial ocean-atmosphere CO₂ exchange.

203

204 **Acknowledgements.** We thank the International Ocean Drilling Program for
205 providing samples from ODP Leg 202, R. Gersonde for the PS2498-1 core material, J.
206 F. McManus for sharing his unpublished benthic isotope data for ODP1238, and E. J.
207 Rohling, M. P. Hain, and C. Beaulieu for instructive discussions. For the calibration
208 of *G. bulloides*, we thank M. Kucera for providing core top samples from the archives
209 at the University of Tübingen, H. C. Bostock for samples from the National Institute
210 for Water and Atmospheric Research (NIWA), Wellington, and B. J. Marshall and R.
211 Thunell (University of South Carolina) for samples from the Cariaco Basin sediment
212 trap time series. J. A. Milton, M. J. Cooper, and A. Michalik provided assistance
213 during IPC-MS analyses and sample preparation in the laboratory. C. Alt and M. T.
214 Horigome helped with foraminifera picking. We thank the other members of ‘The B-
215 Team’ at the National Oceanography Centre Southampton for their contributions.
216 Financial support was provided by the European Community through a Marie Curie
217 Intra-European Fellowship for Career Development to M.A.M.B., the Universitat
218 Autònoma de Barcelona through a Postdoctoral Research Grant to G.M., the Spanish
219 Ministry of Science and Innovation (PROCARSO project) to G.M., P.Z., P.G.M., a
220 NERC PhD studentship awarded to M.J.H., a NOAA/UCAR Climate and Global
221 Change Postdoctoral Fellowship to J.W.B.R, and NERC grant NE/D00876/X2 to
222 G.L.F. G.M. was also supported by the Australian Laureate Fellowship project
223 FL120100050 (E.J. Rohling).

224

225

226 **Author contributions.** M.A.M.B., G.M., G.L.F. and P.Z. designed the study; G.M.
227 and M.A.M.B. produced the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ and trace element records for PS2498-1; M.A.M.B.
228 produced the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ and trace element records for ODP1238; G.M. produced the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
229 and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data; M.J.H. developed the *G. bulloides* $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -pH calibration; J.W.B.R.
230 sampled sediment core PS2498-1. M.A.M.B. and G.M. wrote the first draft jointly
231 and all authors contributed to the interpretation and the preparation of the final
232 manuscript.

233

234 **Author Information.** Reprints and permissions information is available at
235 www.nature.com/reprints. The authors declare no competing financial interests.
236 Readers are welcome to comment on the online version of the paper. Correspondence
237 and requests for materials should be addressed to M.A.M.B ([M.A.Martinez-](mailto:M.A.Martinez-Boti@noc.soton.ac.uk)
238 Boti@noc.soton.ac.uk) and G.M. (Gianluca.Marino@anu.edu.au).

239

240

241 **Figure legends**

242 **Figure 1. Location of cores PS2498-1 and ODP1238.** Site locations are overlain on
243 a map⁹ of mean annual $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$.

244

245 **Figure 2. $\delta^{11}\text{B}$, pH, and $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ records from the Subantarctic Atlantic (left) and**
246 **Eastern Equatorial Pacific (right) during the last deglaciation. (a) *Globigerina***
247 ***bulloides* $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ with analytical uncertainties (1σ , dark grey envelope; 2σ , light grey**
248 **envelope); (b) $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -based pH (blue) reconstruction for PS-2498-1 and calculated**
249 **seawater pH in equilibrium with atmospheric⁵ $p\text{CO}_2$ ($p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$) (green curve) at the**
250 **same site; (c) $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -derived $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ ($p\text{CO}_2^{\text{sw}}-p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$). Black circle denotes present-**

251 day annual average $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ at PS2498-1 location⁹; **(d)** *G. bulloides* Mg/Ca-based sea
 252 surface temperature (SST); **(e)** and **(j)** $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ from Antarctic ice cores⁵; **(f)**
 253 *Globigerinoides sacculifer* $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ with analytical uncertainties (1σ , dark grey shading;
 254 2σ , light grey shading); **(g)** $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -based pH (red) for ODP1238 and calculated
 255 seawater pH in equilibrium with $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$ (ref.⁵) (green curve). **(h)** $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -based $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$.
 256 Black circle denotes present-day mean annual $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ at ODP1238 location⁹. **(i)** *G.*
 257 *sacculifer* Mg/Ca-based SST. The Late Holocene data in **(f)**, **(g)**, and **(h)** have been
 258 averaged (individual measurements are shown as empty red circles) (see [Methods](#)).
 259 Envelopes in **(b)**, **(c)**, **(g)**, and **(h)** are 68% and 95% uncertainty bounds (light blue/red
 260 shading and dotted lines, respectively) based on a LOESS regression of the $\delta^{11}\text{B}$ -
 261 derived records using a Monte Carlo approach; thick line denotes the maximum
 262 probability fit to the data. YD: Younger Dryas; BA: Bølling-Allerød; ACR: Antarctic
 263 Cold Reversal; HS1: Heinrich Stadial 1; LGM: Last Glacial Maximum. Filled
 264 triangles at the bottom indicate calibrated ^{14}C ages (see [Methods](#)).

265

266

267 **Figure 3. $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ records from the Subantarctic Atlantic (left) and the**
 268 **Eastern Equatorial Pacific (right) during the last deglaciation compared to opal**
 269 **fluxes, $p\text{CO}_2^{\text{atm}}$, and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{atmosphere}}$. **(a)** surface ocean $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ reconstruction for**
 270 **PS2498-1; **(b)** opal fluxes for TN057-13-4PC (Antarctic Zone)⁴; **(c)** PS2498-1**
 271 ***Globigerina bulloides* $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (blue dots) with a LOESS non-parametric regression of**
 272 **the data (span = 0.4) (solid line); **(d)** and **(j)** atmospheric CO_2 concentrations from**
 273 **Antarctic ice cores⁵; **(e)** and **(k)** atmospheric $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ record from Antarctic ice cores⁵; **(f)****
 274 **surface ocean $\Delta p\text{CO}_2$ reconstruction in ODP1238; **(g)** opal fluxes for V19-30 (EEP)²⁵;**
 275 ****(h)** and **(i)** ODP1238 *Globigerinoides sacculifer* and *Neogloboquadrina dutertrei***

276 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (pink and electric blue dots, respectively) with a LOESS non-parametric
277 regression of the data (solid lines; span = 0.7 and 0.33, respectively). YD: Younger
278 Dryas; BA: Bølling-Allerød; ACR: Antarctic Cold Reversal; HS1: Heinrich Stadial 1;
279 LGM: Last Glacial Maximum.

280

281 **References**

282

- 283 1 Köhler, P., Fischer, H., Munhoven, G. & Zeebe, R. E. Quantitative
284 interpretation of atmospheric carbon records over the last glacial termination.
285 *Global Biogeochem. Cycles* **19**, GB4020 (2005).
- 286 2 Yu, J. *et al.* Loss of carbon from the deep sea since the Last Glacial Maximum.
287 *Science* **330**, 1084-1087 (2010).
- 288 3 Sigman, D. M., Hain, M. P. & Haug, G. H. The polar ocean and glacial cycles
289 in atmospheric CO_2 concentration. *Nature* **466**, 47-55 (2010).
- 290 4 Anderson, R. F. *et al.* Wind-driven upwelling in the Southern Ocean and the
291 deglacial rise in atmospheric CO_2 . *Science* **323**, 1443-1448 (2009).
- 292 5 Schmitt, J. *et al.* Carbon isotope constraints on the deglacial CO_2 rise from ice
293 cores. *Science* **336**, 711-714 (2012).
- 294 6 Burke, A. & Robinson, L. F. The Southern Ocean's role in carbon exchange
295 during the last deglaciation. *Science* **335**, 557-561 (2012).
- 296 7 Spero, H. J. & Lea, D. W. The cause of carbon isotope minimum events on
297 glacial terminations. *Science* **296**, 522-525 (2002).
- 298 8 Sarmiento, J. L., Gruber, N., Brzezinski, M. A. & Dunne, J. P. High-latitude
299 controls of thermocline nutrients and low latitude biological productivity.
300 *Nature* **427**, 56-60 (2004).

- 301 9 Takahashi, T. *et al.* Climatological mean and decadal change in surface ocean
302 pCO₂, and net sea-air CO₂ flux over the global oceans. *Deep-Sea Res. Pt. I* **56**,
303 2075-2076 (2009).
- 304 10 Keeling, R. F. & Visbeck, M. Palaeoceanography - Antarctic stratification and
305 glacial CO₂. *Nature* **412**, 605-606 (2001).
- 306 11 Martínez-García, A. *et al.* Links between iron supply, marine productivity, sea
307 surface temperature, and CO₂ over the last 1.1 Ma. *Paleoceanography* **24**,
308 PA1207 (2009).
- 309 12 Pichevin, L. E. *et al.* Enhanced carbon pump inferred from relaxation of
310 nutrient limitation in the glacial ocean. *Nature* **459**, 1114-1198 (2009).
- 311 13 Ninnemann, U. S. & Charles, C. D. Regional differences in Quaternary
312 Subantarctic nutrient cycling: Link to intermediate and deep water ventilation.
313 *Paleoceanography* **12**, 560-567 (1997).
- 314 14 Pena, L. D., Cacho, I., Ferretti, P. & Hall, M. A. El Niño-Southern Oscillation-
315 like variability during glacial terminations and interlatitudinal teleconnections.
316 *Paleoceanography* **23**, PA3101 (2008).
- 317 15 Hönisch, B. & Hemming, N. G. Surface ocean pH response to variations in
318 pCO₂ through two full glacial cycles. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **236**, 305-314
319 (2005).
- 320 16 Foster, G. L. Seawater pH, pCO₂ and [CO₂⁻³] variations in the Caribbean Sea
321 over the last 130 kyr: A boron isotope and B/Ca study of planktic foraminifera.
322 *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **271**, 254-266 (2008).
- 323 17 Marshall, J. & Speer, K. Closure of the meridional overturning circulation
324 through Southern Ocean upwelling. *Nature Geosci.* **5**, 171-180 (2012).

- 325 18 Toggweiler, J. R., Dixon, K. & Broecker, W. S. The Peru upwelling and the
326 ventilation of the South Pacific thermocline. *J. Geophys. Res.-Oceans* **96**,
327 20467-20497 (1991).
- 328 19 Goodman, P. J., Hazeleger, W., De Vries, P. & Cane, M. Pathways into the
329 Pacific Equatorial Undercurrent: A trajectory analysis. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.* **35**,
330 2134-2151 (2005).
- 331 20 Liu, Z. Y. & Yang, H. J. Extratropical control of tropical climate, the
332 atmospheric bridge and oceanic tunnel. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **30**, 1230 (2003).
- 333 21 Zeebe, R. E. & Wolf-Gladrow, D. A. *CO₂ in Seawater: Equilibrium, Kinetics,*
334 *Isotopes.* (Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2001).
- 335 22 Palmer, M. R. & Pearson, P. N. A 23,000-year record of surface water pH and
336 PCO₂ in the western equatorial Pacific Ocean. *Science* **300**, 480-482 (2003).
- 337 23 Kubota, K., Yokoyama, Y., Ishikawa, T., Obrochta, S. & Suzuki, A. Larger
338 CO₂ source at the equatorial Pacific during the last deglaciation. *Sci. Rep.* **4**,
339 5261 (2014).
- 340 24 Douville, E. *et al.* Abrupt sea surface pH change at the end of the Younger
341 Dryas in the central sub-equatorial Pacific inferred from boron isotope
342 abundance in corals (*Porites*). *Biogeosciences* **7**, 2445-2459 (2010).
- 343 25 Bradtmiller, L. I., Anderson, R. F., Fleisher, M. Q. & Burckle, L. H. Diatom
344 productivity in the equatorial Pacific Ocean from the last glacial period to the
345 present: A test of the silicic acid leakage hypothesis. *Paleoceanography* **21**,
346 PA4201 (2006).
- 347 26 Palter, J. B., Sarmiento, J. L., Gnanadesikan, A., Simeon, J. & Slater, R. D.
348 Fueling export production: nutrient return pathways from the deep ocean and

349 their dependence on the Meridional Overturning Circulation. *Biogeosciences* **7**,
350 3549-3568 (2010).

351 27 Rae, J. W. B. *et al.* Deep water formation in the North Pacific and deglacial
352 CO₂ rise. *Paleoceanography* **29**, 645-667 (2014).

353 28 Menviel, L. & Joos, F. Toward explaining the Holocene carbon dioxide and
354 carbon isotope records: Results from transient ocean carbon cycle-climate
355 simulations. *Paleoceanography* **27**, PA1207 (2012).

356 29 Barker, S. *et al.* Interhemispheric Atlantic seesaw response during the last
357 deglaciation. *Nature* **457**, 1097-1150 (2009).

358 30 Denton, G. H. *et al.* The last glacial termination. *Science* **328**, 1652-1656
359 (2010).

360 31 McGee, D., Marcantonio, F. & Lynch-Stieglitz, J. Deglacial changes in dust
361 flux in the eastern equatorial Pacific. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* **257**, 215-230
362 (2007).

363 32 Reimer, P. J. *et al.* IntCal13 and Marine13 radiocarbon age calibration curves
364 0-50,000 years cal BP. *Radiocarbon* **55**, 1869-1887 (2013).

365

366

